

EFFECT OF SURFACE MORPHOLOGY ON FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF ADHESIVELY BONDED CARBON FIBRES PEEK COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Sandblasting, PEEK carbon fibres composite, surface treatment, surface morphology, adhesive bonding, cyclic fatigue.*

Abstract

In this paper, experimental fatigue behaviour of adhesively bonded PEEK composite was investigated. PEEK based materials are considered as a high performance thermoplastic materials conferring to their good mechanical properties and chemical resistant for many aggressive environments due to their semi-crystallinity property. However, it is well known that the adhesive bonding assembly of this kind of materials is difficult without an appropriate surface preparation. In the objective of enhancing the mechanical properties in cyclic fatigue of adhesively joined PEEK, sandblasting surface treatment was applied. The effect of sandblasting conditions on surface morphology was presented. Joint durability and fatigue life was expressed in terms of Wöhler curves according to surface preparation condition. In the end, an energetically approach was used to determine joint microstructural evolution in cyclic long term loading.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, adhesive bonding technology appears to be an appropriate alternative for assembling composite parts. In fact this method offers many advantages such as uniform stress distribution along the joint and minimizing stress concentration, joining dissimilar materials, weight reduction compared with other joining methods.

High performance semi-crystalline thermoplastics (PolyEtherEtherKetone (PEEK)) reinforced fibres are increasingly used in aeronautical industry due to their high toughness and recyclability.

The good chemical resistance of such thermoplastic composites makes their adhesive bonding resistance poor and, surface treatment before bonding is a primary step to achieve satisfactory joints [1].

Low cost, environmental friendly and easy to implement technique makes sandblasting treatment one of competitive methods for preparing thermoplastic material surfaces before adhesive bonding [2].

For many structural systems such as adhesive bonding, fatigue behaviour is certainly an important type of loading to consider. Indeed cyclic loading fatigue may produce failure of adhesive-bonded assemblies at lower stress level than they can tolerate under monotonic loading. Therefore Fatigue analysis and life time service prediction are highly required especially in the case of damage tolerance design of adhesive bonded systems based on PEEK composites for aeronautic applications. For this purpose two principal approaches are used: the first is based on the measurements of crack growth rate of pre-cracked adhesive joint subjected to mode I, II [3-5] or mixed-mode fatigue loading. The second approach consists in determining, the stress versus the number of cycles to failure curves usually named Stress-Number of cycle (S-N) curves or Wöhler curves.

The effect of substrate surface state and nature [6-7] on the fatigue performance of adhesive joints has been investigated by different authors. It was shown that the relationship between surface texture and adhesion is very complex. In the purpose of optimizing abrasive surface treatment processes, different mechanisms and their interactions need to be understood [8, 17]. In this paper, the effect of

surface morphology generated by sandblasting process, on the long term behaviour of adhesively bonded PEEK composite single shear lap-joint specimen, under cyclic loading (fatigue) was studied. In-situ fatigue cycle monitoring allowed determining fatigue life and damage states of bonded joint. The cross correlation between interface (substrate/adhesive) properties and the fatigue performance of joints was discussed.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Continuous carbon fibres reinforced PEEK composites as substrate were investigated. This kind of materials begins to be widely used in aeronautical industry.

Fig 1. Schematic representation of PEEK composite with quasi-isotropic layup (a), and Optical micrograph showing the stacking sequence of PEEK APC-2 (b).

The PEEK composite studied is made from 16 plies of unidirectional PEEK reinforced by high resistance carbon fibres (AS4) prepreg manufactured by Cytac® named APC-2 and is supplied by Airbus® France; The configuration of the laminates is quasi-

isotropic and the stacking sequence is as follows: [+45/0/-45/90/+45/0/-45/90]_s as shown in Fig.1.

The PEEK matrix melt viscosity is approximately like the PEEK 150G commercialized by Victrex. It is characterized by middle molecular weight compared to other PEEK references, which facilitates fibre impregnation. The structural adhesive used was a commercial epoxy based two parts adhesive (3M 9323-2 B/A) generally used in aeronautical applications. Curing cycle is as follows: 2 hours at 65°C, as recommended by the manufacturer.

2.2 Thermal characterization

DSC analysis was carried out using the DSC STAR 01 module from METTLER TOLEDO with a 25°C to 400°C temperature range and a heating rate of 10°C/min. In semi-crystalline polymers the degree of crystallinity is an important factor, since the mechanical behaviour of these materials is linked to the crystallinity degree [9]. The degree of crystallinity was calculated using the following relationship:

$$X_c = \frac{Q_m}{\Delta W Q_c} 100 \quad (1)$$

where X_c is the degree of crystallinity (%), Q_m is the melting enthalpy [J.g⁻¹], Q_c is the melting enthalpy for fully crystallized PEEK ($Q_c=130$ Jg⁻¹ [10]) and ΔW is the weight content of PEEK in the composite. In this case ΔW is about 30±2% measured by two different methods: double weighing (in air and distillate water) and optical method associated with image analysis.

Fig 2. DSC thermogram of PEEK APC-2.

Fig.2 illustrates an example of DSC thermogram showing glass transition inflection and melt endothermic peak.

This figure shows that the studied PEEK APC-2 is characterized by a glass transition, T_g , of about 152°C determined from the mid-point. Crystallinity degree calculated by equation (Eq.2) nearly 37%. The melting point of PEEK APC-2 was determined at the peak of endothermic transition: $342 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The absence of exothermic peak before glass transition indicates that the composite is crystallised at its maximum.

The cured adhesive was also analysed by DSC. The result shows that the adhesive is fully polymerised and its glass transition, T_g is $66 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ (midpoint).

2.3 Rheological characterization

Dynamical Mechanical Analysis (DMA) tests were performed with DMA50 0.1dB from METRAVIB. Specimens were prepared from laminates as rectangular bars ($20\text{mm} \times 2\text{mm} \times 1.5\text{mm}$) and were subjected to tensile/compression loading at controlled alternating strain. The temperature range was 25°C to 280°C with a heating rate of $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the frequency was 10 Hz.

Fig.3 shows the evolutions of storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan(\delta)$) as a function of temperature.

Fig 3. Storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan(\delta)$) versus temperature of PEEK APC-2 composite at (10 Hz).

In the analysed temperature, the $\tan(\delta)$ spectrum exhibits a broad peak which maximum is located at about 170°C (10 Hz), which corresponds to the main or α -relaxation associated with the glass transition. In the same temperature range, a very slight decrease in storage modulus (E') with temperature was observed. These results, which are consistent with

DSC analysis confirm that APC-2 PEEK QI composites are high performance materials, which exhibit good mechanical properties up to 250°C .

2.4 Sandblasting treatment

The studied materials were subjected to dry sandblasting (particles projection) with varying experimental conditions (particle size, projection duration).

Schematic principle of sandblasting process is shown in Fig 4. The following results were obtained for subsequent fixed operating conditions: ceramic jet nozzle of 8 mm diameter, applied air pressure is about 5 bars, the distance L between the nozzle and target is 80 mm and the impact angle is 90° . The influence of process duration and abrasive particle sizes were examined.

Fig 4. Schematic setup of sandblasting device.

Projection duration was varied as follow: 5, 10, 20, 30 and 45 seconds and three different particle sizes ($50\mu\text{m}$, $110\mu\text{m}$ and $250\mu\text{m}$) were used in the aim to investigate the surface morphology evolution as a function of surface treatment process conditions.

Abrasive particles (commercially named corundum) are composed chemically by 99% of alumina (Al_2O_3) and have an irregular shape with abrasive angles.

After abrasive treatment all samples were cleaned ultrasonically with ethanol for 15min to eliminate any particles and dust presented on surfaces before surface characterization and bonding tests.

2.5 Surface morphology analyses

The effect of sandblasting process on surface morphology was studied using two surface characterisation techniques.

The surface SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) analysis was performed in order to illustrate visually the surface morphological changes after sandblasting

and interactions between particles and PEEK APC-2. Surface roughness parameters of untreated and treated surfaces were characterized by using a 3D optical white light interferometer, from Veeco topometer type WYCO 9300. The analyses are based on non-contact vertical scanning interferometry (VSI) measurement mode [11].

Topographical 3D parameters were calculated according to the following standards, defining Geometrical Product Specifications (GPS): ISO 12085, ISO 25178, ISO 13565 and ISO 12181 [12]. The most pertinent parameters were selected.

Calculation of 3D morphological parameters constitutes an unique way to evaluate topographical modifications due to sandblasting in particularly anisotropy characteristics and surface morphology.

2.6 Adhesive joint monotonic and fatigue tests

In order to evaluate mechanical behaviour of the adhesively bonded system (APC-2/Epoxy/APC-2), the single lap shear configuration test was chosen, due to its simplicity to implement and reproducibility. The single lap shear test is the most used method as comparative test in the case of adhesive bonding strength evaluation.

Fig 5. Schematic representation of adhesively bonded single lap shear specimen.

Specimens for single-lap shear test were prepared from two samples of PEEK APC-2 of 106 mm long, 25 mm wide and 3 mm thick bonded along 12.5 mm according to the international standard ISO 4587:2003 (cf. Fig. 6). A specific device was designed to make easy the realization of the bonded

specimens. The overlap joint and the adhesive thickness ($200 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$) were carefully controlled after manufacturing. After sandblasting treatment application, the substrates were ultrasonically cleaned with ethanol for 15 min before bonding.

The monotonic tensile shear strength of the adhesively bonded single lap joints was measured using a MTS Bionix (Model 370.02) axial/torsion tester equipped with a 25 kN load cell and a displacement sensor at room temperature ($23 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min.

Tension-Tension load controlled fatigue tests were performed in the same metrological device. The frequency was maintained constant at 10 Hz for all tested configurations, and the fatigue loading ratio (R-ratio) was 0.1. However, if the failure did not occur before 10^6 cycles the test was stopped. The fatigue test criterion was assembly failure. The maximum stress level was varied from the monotonic maximum strength of the adhesively bonded single lap joints.

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Morphological analyses

Fig 6 shows SEM analyses of untreated and sandblasted surfaces.

The surfaces are characterized by a complex and anisotropic morphology due to the quasi-isotropic sequence stacking of the laminate, with the surface ply oriented at 45° , and the morphology of the prepreg. Indeed continuous fibre thermoplastic prepreg are made from bundles of continuous fibres each touching the neighbouring row and hot-melt coating. This results in a surface layer of the laminate with two fibre volume fraction zones with a lower reinforcement content at the inter-bundle regions than anywhere else (Fig. 6.a). The sandblasting treatment increases surface anisotropy and complexity as shown by SEM (Fig. 6 b-c), the low fibre density zones being less resistant to abrasion.

Fig 6. SEM micrographics showing PEEK APC-2 surfaces: untreated (a), sandblasted during 5 seconds and 50 μm particle sizes (b) and sandblasted during 10 seconds and 250 μm particle sizes (c).

SEM analysis shows that the increase of projection duration and the average abrasive particle sizes increase the damage of the composites surface including fibres fractures as illustrated in Fig 7.

Fig 7. SEM micrographic showing sandblasted composite PEEK APC2. Treatment duration for 10 seconds with an average particle size of 250μm.

In the aim to evaluate quantitatively surface morphological modification due to sandblasting conditions, interferometry technique was used.

Fig. 8. Surface morphologies and relevant anisotropies a) before treatment, c) sandblasted.

Surface anisotropic specificity of PEEK APC-2 determines the choice of surface topography analysis. Indeed, it is difficult to better represent an anisotropic surface topography (Fig. 8), based on a 2D profiles, because in this case the measured surfaces have not the same roughness characteristics according to the axis (x) and to its orthogonal axis (y). Therefore, the calculation was focused on 3D roughness parameters which are more representative of analysed surfaces.

From more than hundred parameters of surface morphological characterization, only the most pertinent parameters were selected. The roughness

parameters used are based on better representative parameters, as surface amplitude and peak valley distribution. Generally, classical used parameters to describe surface roughness are surface amplitude parameters as: S_a , S_q and S_z . All these parameters give information about surface heights. In this paper the classical amplitude parameter S_q was selected.

This parameter is defined by international standard ISO 25178 of 3D topography data and defined as the root mean square (RMS) of surface heights (cf. Eq.2) corresponding to R_q in 2D profile analysis defined in international standard ISO 4287.

$$S_q = \sqrt{\iint_A (Z(x, y))^2 dx dy} \quad (2)$$

where A corresponds to the defined measured area and $Z(x,y)$ are the different heights according to x and y directions.

The variation of the parameter S_q (μm) as function of projection and all particle sizes is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig 9. S_q evolution as a function of treatment duration and average particle sizes.

This Figure shows that the surface heights increase significantly with treatment duration for all average particle sizes. Beyond a treatment duration of 5 seconds there is no obvious correlation between the average particle size and surface morphology, resulting probably from composite high-level damage state involving a large amount of fibre breaks as mentioned previously. Conversely, for projection duration of 5s, the parameter S_q increases continuously with particle size, but this effect is not significant. In order, to better describe the surface morphology other 3D roughness parameters were investigated. One of those morphological parameters is the surface density of summits (S_{ds}). This

parameter is defined in European standard EUR 15178N. S_{ds} is the number of summits of an unit sampling area; a peak is defined as a summit if it is higher than its eight nearest neighbours [13].

Fig 10 shows the S_{ds} evolution as a function of average particle sizes and projection duration. The results illustrate that the density of summits (S_{ds}) decreases while increasing the average particle size. This phenomenon is due to the particles foot-print on the substrate after impact. Indeed, the increase of particle size leads to large imprints and therefore the distance between neighbour peaks is high and the density of summits per unit of area is small.

Fig 10. Density of summits evolution as a function of average particle sizes and projection time.

To achieve different levels of adhesion, the different assemblies PEEK APC-2/Epoxy/PEEK APC-2 were manufactured by varying the substrate treatment. To this end, the treatment duration was limited to 5s in order to prevent for damage, and the average particle sizes were varied (50, 110 and 250 μm).

3.2 Monotonic mechanical properties of adhesive joint

The shear strength is calculated using the following relationship:

$$\tau = \frac{F}{A} \quad (3)$$

where F (N) is the ultimate load of the load versus displacement curve of bonded lap joint and A (mm^2) is the overlap area. The results are summarized in Tab. 1. The single lap shear strength corresponds to the arithmetic average of six tests.

Tab. 1. Single lap shear strength of PEEK APC-2

Average particle sizes	Untreated	50µm	110µm	250µm
Lap shear strength (MPa)	11.5	28.5	27	27.5
Standard deviation (MPa)	3	0.3	0.1	1

Tab. 1 shows that the single lap shear strength is very sensitive to substrate treatment. The average shear strength of the assembly without any treatment is below 12 MPa, whereas it increases up to 28MPa after substrate sandblasting treatment. Nevertheless, the variation of average particle sizes has low influence on the shear strength.

The joints fail adhesively for untreated assembly and the failure surface features show a mixed failure mode in the case of treated substrates.

3.3 Adhesive joint fatigue test

Loading levels were varied from about 16 MPa to about 7 MPa. Six specimens were tested for each load level and surface treatment configuration.

S-N curve and morphology

Experimental fatigue data are represented as a plot of stress (S) as a function of the number of cycles to failure (N) or S-N curve also known as Wöhler curve. Fig. 11 gives the S-N curves for all the tested configurations.

Fig. 11. Wöhler curves as a function of average particle sizes (bonded PEEK APC-2).

The effect of substrate treatment on fatigue is more significant than on monotonic failure. The surfaces treated with an average particle size around 50 µm show the best behaviour. This trend is however attenuated as the mean stress decreases as shown by the convergence of the S-N curves at high cycles. Moreover, the results show larger scatter at high stress amplitude (low cycle fatigue) than at high cycle fatigue contrary to what is generally observed for bulk materials.

As for monotonic loading failure surfaces show a mixed mode failure, indicating high enough interfacial bonding. There is no general tendency concerning the ratio of cohesive fracture surface except at high cycles for which the failure mode is predominantly cohesive in the adhesive layer.

These observations give indications regarding differences in the S-N curves: the high scatter of the cycles to failure in the low cycle domain and the tendency toward a common behaviour in the long term. As failure occurs mainly within the adhesive layer for long time tests, the failure mode is not much affected by substrate treatment. For other amplitude levels for which the failure mode is mixed the adhesive-substrate interface is more involved in the failure process.

The functional peaks density (S_{ds}) on treated surfaces which is the highest in this case of treatment with average particle size of 50 mm is probably responsible of the best fatigue behaviour, the adhesive-substrate interface being mainly associated with mechanical interlocking. The different behaviour between monotonic and cyclic loading can be attributed to the fact that the fatigue crack growth likely took place by crack arrest and subsequent propagation for which the mechanical interlocking is a key parameter.

In-situ analysis of load displacement curves

Fatigue behaviour of adhesive bonded joint was investigated by in-situ monitoring load-displacement data as a function of cycles (cf. Fig.12).

Fig. 12. Fatigue cycle of adhesively bonded composites.

From these cycles several physical data can be calculated [14]:

- E_d : dissipated energy per cycle which can be quantified by the area inside the fatigue cycle.
- E_t : total energy, calculated using the following equation $E_t = (F_{max} - F_{min}) \times (D_{max} - D_{min})$.
- the system stiffness (R_s) [N/m], which is calculated by the general slope of the cycle and defined by the following equation:

$$R_s = \frac{F_{max} - F_{min}}{D_{max} - D_{min}} \quad (4)$$

Their variation may be related to a structural change at the microscopic scale in the substrate/adhesive junction or any of the components, as well as initiation and growth of microscopic cracks [15].

Fig. 13. Dissipated energy evolution as a function of number of cycle (load = 9MPa) during fatigue tests.

Fig. 13 gives an example of the changes in dissipated energy (E_d) per cycle as a function of the number of cycles until assembly failure at a loading level of about 9 MPa according to different average particle sizes.

The results show a decrease of the dissipated energy versus time until a minimum threshold where energy increases up to joint failure. This trend is observed for all stress levels studied and all surface treatments.

The evolution of the stiffness against the number of cycles was plotted in Fig. 14 in the case of maximum load of about 11 MPa and the three average particle sizes used. The stiffness increases slightly during fatigue up to a certain threshold where it abruptly drops up to sample failure. This result is consistent with the changes in dissipated energy.

Fig. 14. Evolution of the stiffness of the system during fatigue tests according to the number of cycles (load = 11MPa). The average particle size is varied from 50 to 250µm.

From dissipated energy and stiffness changes of the system analysis during fatigue life, two stages of fatigue are observed (cf. Fig 15).

Fig 15. Fatigue behaviour versus cycle number.

• Stage I which corresponds to the drop of the dissipated energy and the increase in the stiffness of the assembly. The decrease of the dissipated energy during a fatigue test is probably associated to structural changes in the adhesive. Additional crosslinking was not considered as DSC analysis on epoxy adhesive before fatigue, shows that the adhesive is fully polymerized. This result leads us to consider the occurrence of sub- T_g structural relaxation phenomenon or physical aging observed in glasses [16]. This phenomenon will lead to compaction and densification of the network at a temperature close to the glass transition temperature, as well as changes in physical and mechanical properties. The changes in the molecular structure of epoxy adhesive may be responsible of the changes in assembly mechanical properties during fatigue test. This assumption was confirmed by the presence of an endothermic peak on a DSC thermogram of adhesive after fatigue test.

• Stage II is the increase in dissipated energy and a significant decrease in stiffness of the system. Likely, this stage coincides with the massive initiation and propagation of micro-cracks under the effect of the cyclic loading until assembly failure.

4. Conclusion

Fatigue behaviour of adhesively bonded PEEK composite was studied. The good chemical resistance of PEEK based materials makes their adhesive bonding resistance low, and surface treatment is essential to achieve structural joints. The effects of sandblasting surface treatment on lap shear strength were investigated in a first step. In a second stage in situ analysis of the joint behaviour during fatigue was examined using continuously monitoring of dissipated energy and stiffness

The following conclusions can be drawn:

- Use sandblasting surface treatments lead to improve significantly fatigue life of CFR (PEEK) adhesively bonded system especially for high stress level. A correlation between pertinent morphological parameters and adhesive bonding behaviour was found.
- Monitoring fatigue cycle parameters lead to the identification of two successive stages in fatigue life of adhesively bonded joints: a first stage associated to the microstructural

changes in the adhesive and a second stage associated to the propagation of macroscopic damage.

Acknowledgment

This work has been supported by a grant from DGCIS-FUI (INMAT) managed by AIRBUS - France. The authors would like to express a special recognition to Digital Surf® - French Company for their assistance in data treatments.

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